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BODY MASS INDEX AMONG THE PATIENTS PRESENTING IN OUTDOOR DEPARTMENT

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ABSTRACT:

Body mass index (BMI) is a value derived from the mass (weight) and height of a person. The BMI is defined as the body mass divided by the square of the body height and is universally expressed in units of kg/m², resulting from mass in kilograms and height in meters. This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, height, and weight of all the patients were noted on a predefined proforma. A total of 100 patients presenting in the emergency department were included in this study i.e., 50 males (50%) and 50 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 31.45±3.22 years. Out of these patients, five patients have BMI between 25-30 and were labelled as overweight, four were in between 30-35 and were labelled as obese class 1, twenty patients were underweighted i.e., BMI<18.5 and rest of the patients were having normal weight i.e., 18.5 to 25.

Keyword: BMI, Body Mass Index

INTRODUCTION:

Body mass index (BMI) is a value derived from the mass (weight) and height of a person. The BMI is defined as the body mass divided by the square of the body height and is universally expressed in units of kg/m^2 , resulting from mass in kilograms and height in meters. The BMI may be determined using a table or chart which displays BMI as a function of mass and height using contour lines or colors for different BMI categories, and which may use other units of measurement.

The BMI is a convenient rule of thumb used to broadly categorize a person as underweight, normal weight, overweight, or obese based on tissue mass (muscle, fat, and bone) and height. Commonly accepted BMI ranges are underweight (under $18.5 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$), normal weight (18.5 to 25), overweight (25 to 30), and obese (over 30). BMIs under 20 and over 25 have been associated with higher all-causes mortality, with the risk increasing with distance from the 20 – 25 range. Adolphe Quetelet, a Belgian astronomer, mathematician, statistician, and sociologist, devised the basis of the BMI between 1830 and 1850 as he developed what he called "social physics".

The modern term "body mass index" (BMI) for the ratio of human body weight to squared height was coined in a paper published in the July 1972 edition of the Journal of Chronic Diseases by Ancel Keys and others. In this paper, Keys argued that what he termed the BMI was "...if not fully satisfactory, at least as good as any other relative weight index as an indicator of relative obesity". The interest in an index that measures body fat came with observed increasing obesity in prosperous Western societies. Keys explicitly judged BMI as appropriate for population studies and inappropriate for individual evaluation. Nevertheless, due to its simplicity, it has come to be widely used for preliminary diagnoses. Additional metrics, such as waist circumference, can be more useful (1-3).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, height, and weight of all the patients were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 100 patients presenting in the emergency department were included in this study i.e., 50 males (50%) and 50 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 31.45 ± 3.22 years. Out of these patients, five patients have BMI between 25-30 and were labelled as overweight, four were in between 30-35 and were labelled as obese class 1, twenty patients were underweighted i.e. $BMI < 18.5$ and rest of the patients were having normal weight i.e. 18.5 to 25.

DISCUSSION:

The BMI is generally used as a means of correlation between groups related by general mass and can serve as a vague means of estimating adiposity. The duality of the BMI is that, while it is easy to use as a general calculation, it is limited as to how accurate and pertinent the data obtained from it can be. Generally, the index is suitable for recognizing trends within sedentary or overweight individuals because there is a smaller margin of error. The BMI has been used by the WHO as the standard for recording obesity statistics since the early 1980s. This general correlation is particularly useful for consensus data regarding obesity or various other conditions because it can be used to build a semi-accurate representation from which a solution can be stipulated, or the RDA for a group can be calculated. Similarly, this is becoming more and more pertinent to the growth of children, due to the fact that the majority of children are sedentary. Cross-sectional studies indicated that sedentary people can decrease BMI by becoming more physically active.

Smaller effects are seen in prospective cohort studies which lend to support active mobility as a means to prevent a further increase in BMI.

BMI categories are generally regarded as a satisfactory tool for measuring whether sedentary individuals are underweight, overweight, or obese with various exceptions, such as: athletes, children, the elderly, and the infirm. Also, the growth of a child is documented against a BMI-measured growth chart. Obesity trends can then be calculated from the difference between the child's BMI and the BMI on the chart. In the United States, BMI is also used as a measure of underweight, owing to advocacy on behalf of those with eating disorders, such as anorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa. In France, Italy, and Spain, legislation has been introduced banning the usage of fashion show models having a BMI below 18. In Israel, a BMI below 18.5 is banned. This is done to fight anorexia among models and people interested in fashion. A study published by Journal of the American Medical Association (JAMA) in 2005 showed that overweight people had a death rate similar to normal weight people as defined by BMI, while underweight and obese people had a higher death rate. A study published by The Lancet in 2009 involving 900,000 adults showed that overweight and underweight people both had a mortality rate higher than normal weight people as defined by BMI. The optimal BMI was found to be in the range of 22.5–25. High BMI is associated with type 2 diabetes only in persons with high serum gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase (4-6).

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